

**NIGERIAN TOURISM INDUSTRY AND GLOBAL COMPETITIVENESS:
CONSTRAINTS AND OPPORTUNITIES**

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Abstract

Despite the numerous calls and studies aimed at enhancing the Nigerian tourism industry for socio-economic sustainability, growth seem lacking as the country was ranked 129 among 140 nations of the world in the Travel and Tourism Competitiveness Index 2019. This result suggests that Nigeria is yet to gain competitive advantage in the global tourism trade. This present study seeks to examine the country's competitive disadvantage through the prism of Porter's (1990) Diamond Model. The study analysed each of the four determinants of the Porter's diamond model to highlight degree of contribution of each of the determinants to the competitive disadvantage of the tourism industry in Nigeria. The study proposes academic, stakeholder and marketing implications for the study.

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